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10. SHANKARPUR PLATE OF BUDHAGUPTA AND HARIVARMAN : Gupta Year 166¹

Balchandra Jain

The plate which is being published here was found sometime before June 1977 at the village Shankarpur in the Gopadavanasa tahsil of the Sidhi district of Madhya Pradesh by a village-boy who handed it over to the Principal of the nearby Higher Secondary School at Niwas in the same district. The said Principal deposited the plate in the Collector's office at Sidhi. The discovery was reported to Shri Veda Prakash Nagaich, Registering Officer of the Madhya Pradesh Archaeology and Museums Department, Rewa who obtained the plate from Sidhi Collectorate and forwarded the same to me for examination and study. I edit the record from the original plate as hereunder.

This is a single plate measuring 24 cms in breadth and 11 cms in height. The weight of the plate is 275 grms. The writing on the plate is in a good state of preservation.

The plate is inscribed on one side only. Its right top and bottom corners are damaged and broken off, causing loss of four letters in the first line, one in the second line and two or more in the last line. There is a small round hole about $\frac{1}{2}$ cm in diameter in the middle of the left side in between the fifth and sixth lines for the seal-ring to pass. The seal is now missing.

The plate contains ten lines of writing. The average size of the letters is $\frac{3}{4}$ cm. They are deeply engraved and show through the back of the plate.

The characters are of the Northern variety of the Brāhmī script of the 5th centu-

ry A. D. and generally resemble those of the Khoh Copper plate inscription of *Mahārāja* Hastin, Gupta year 163.² The forms of *r* and *j* are of the earlier variety in majority of the cases. Medial *i* has been indicated by a semi-circular mark above the letter and an additional dot inside shows its long form.

The language of the record is Sanskrit. Except for the two imprecatory and benedictive verses in lines 6-8, the whole record is composed in prose. As regards orthography, the consonant following *r* is redoubled in many cases as in *varmma* in lines 3 and 4, and *tārarkka* in line 64, but not in *Sarva* in line 4 and *sarma* in line 10; *s* is used for *ś* and *sh* as in *satē*, *saṣ* in line 1, *viṣṭha* in line 7 and *sarma* in line 10; final *m* is changed into *anusvāra* as in *phalaṁ* in line 8. The initial *u* is seen in line 6. In addition to the above, there are a few more omissions and commissions which have been rectified in the text.

The object of the inscription is to record the grant of the village Chitrapalya by *Mahārāja* Harivarman, son of queen Sarvasvāminī and *Mahārāja* Vijayavarman, grandson of *Mahārāja* Gitavarman³ and probably daughter's son of *Mahārāja* Sātana⁴ (who appears to be a Saka ruler) to the brāhmaṇa Gōsvāmin of the Kautsa-gōtra. The grant was made by issuing the copper plate on a *tithi* (now lost due to damage)⁵ in the month of *Śrāvāṇa* in the year 166⁶ (expressed by words) of an unspecified era during the reign of *Paramadēva* Budhagupta when the year Mahā-Māgha of the 12-year cycle of the Jupiter was current. The village was made

free from all taxes, out of bound for all regular and irregular forces and to be enjoyed as long as the moon, the stars and the sun will endure.

The charter was written by the *dūtaka* Ruyashtarāja who was the son of Nāgasarman and was the *bhōgika* of the sub-division of Bapidra. The name of *mahāpratihāra* Lavaṇa who was also the *Kumārāmātya* and *bhōgika* of the territory of Bhagavad-Rudrachhadi is also mentioned, perhaps as a witness.

As stated above, the inscription refers to the reign of *Paramadēva* Budhagupta who can be identified with *Mahārājādhirāja* Budhagupta of the imperial Gupta family whose Ēraṇ pillar inscription⁶ is dated in the year 165. Evidently, the year 166⁷ given in the present plate is that of the Gupta era and therefore corresponds to 485 A. D. The Mahā-Māgha saṁvatsara of the 12 year cycle of Jupiter was current in the month of *Śrāvāṇa* in 485 A. D.⁷ when the plate under study was given to the donee brāhmaṇa. It is interesting to note that in his Dāmōdarpūr plates⁸, the emperor Budhagupta is styled as *Paramadai-vata* while the present plate gives him the title of *Paramadēva* perhaps in the sense of an overlord.

The inscription is very important as it brings to light a hitherto unknown line of kings with varman-ending names, who were ruling in the Bāghēlakhaṇḍa area of Madhya Pradesh in the 5th century A. D. and who acknowledged the suzerainty of the Imperial Guptas. Names of three rulers of this hitherto unknown dynasty have been mentioned in this record: they are (1) *Mahārāja* Gitavarman, (2) his son *Mahārāja* Vijayavarman and (3) the latter's son *Mahārāja* Hari-

varman who issued the present plate. The name of the dynasty, however, is not mentioned in the inscription. But, it may not be surprising if these kings have had some direct relation with the Maukharis of the Haṛāhā stone inscription⁹ and the Asīrgaṛh copper seal inscription.¹⁰

The Haṛāhā stone inscription was incised in Vikrama 611 (554 A. D.) during the reign of *Īśānavarman* who is said to be the son of *Īśvaravarman*, grandson of *Ādityavarman* and great-grandson of *Harivarman*. The Asīrgaṛh copper seal inscription of *Sarvarvarman* informs us that while *Īśānavarman* and his son *Sarvarvarman* were the *mahārājādhirājas*, their three ancestors including *Harivarman* were mere *mahārājas*. Therefore, it is possible that *Mahārāja* Harivarman of the present plate may be identical with *Mahārāja* Harivarman of the Asīrgaṛh copper seal who has been highly praised in the Maukhari records. If so, the dynastic history of the Maukharis would go back to the second quarter of the 5th century A. D. when they were ruling in Bāghēlkhāṇḍ as the feudatories of the Guptas. Thus *Mahārāja* Gitavarman,¹¹ grandfather of *Mahārāja* Harivarman, was probably a senior contemporary of Skandagupta.¹² The present plate also throws light on the original home of the Maukharis.

The inscription informs us that *Sarvasvāminī*, the mother of *Harivarman*, was the daughter of *Mahārāja* Sātana. The letter following the name Sātana is broken away but the first letter in the next line is *ka*. Presuming that the lost letter in line 2 was a *sa*, the king appears to be a Saka but I am not certain about the same.¹³

The localities mentioned in the inscription are the *bhōgas* of Bhagavad-Rudra-

chhadi and Bapidra. The first may have some relation with the famous temple of Rudra situated at the place but can not be identified for the present. Bapidra is similar to Gōpadra, probably the ancient name of the river Gōpad flowing nearby the find-spot of the plate. Its exact situ-

ation, however, is not known. The donated village Chitrapalya also remains unidentified. Like Vyāghrapallikā, Chhardapallika, Nāgadēya and Maṇināgapēṭha of the inscriptions of the Uchchakalpa *Mahārajas*,¹⁴ this village has its name after a wild animal, *chitra* (Hindī *chita*).

TEXT¹⁵

- 1 Siddham¹⁶ [||*] samvatsara-(śa)tēsa(sha)ṭsa(ṭsha)ṣṭyu(shṭhyu)ttarē¹⁷ Mahā-māgha-samvatsara(rē) Śrāvaṇa...
- 2 myām paramadēva-Budhaguptē rājani asyām divasa-pūrvāyām śrī-mahārāja-Sāṭana Sa[Śa] -¹⁸
- 3 ka-[dauhi]¹⁹tē(trē)na śrī-mahārāja-Gītavarma-pautrēṇa śrī-mahārāja-Vijayavarmma-sutē[na]
- 4 mahādēvyā[m] Śarvasvāminyām = utpannēna śrī-mahārāja-Harivammaṇā asya brāhmaṇa-Kau[tsa]-
- 5 sagōtra-Gōsvāmina [ē]tach-Chitrapalya tāmu(mra)paṭṭēn = āgrahārō = tisṛishṭaḥ akaraḥ achāṭa-bhaṭa-prā-
- 6 vēśyaḥ[||*] chandra-tār-ārka-samakāliyaḥ Uktañcha bhagavatāVyāsēna[||*] Svadattām = paradattām = vā yō
- 7 harēta vasundharā(rām) [||*] Sva(sa) viṣṭhā(shṭha)yā (yām) kṛimir-bhūtvā piṭribhiḥ saha majyatē[||*] Bahubhirv = vasudhā
- 8 bhuktā rājabhiḥ Sagar-ādibhi(bhiḥ) [||*] Yasya yasya yadā bhūmis = tasya tasya tadā phalaṁ(lam) [||*]
- 9 Kumārāmātya-Bhagavad-rudrachhadi-bhōgika-mahāpratihāra-Lavaṇaḥ Bapidra-bhōgika(kē)[na]
- 10 dūtaka(kē)na likhitam Ruyashṭarājēna²⁰ Nāgasa(śa)ṛma-su[tēna*] [||*]

Notes:

- 1 [See Note 17 below where the date of this charter is correctly read as [Gupta] year 168.—K. V. Ramesh].
- 2 *C.II.*, Vol. III, No. 22
- 3 The reading of the first letter of the name Gītavarman is not certain. [The reading of the last 2 and the first five letters in line 3 of the text is *Sāla*(or *rya*)*na kul-ōdbhūtēna*. Thus [Gī]tavarman is here described as a descendant of *Mahārāja Sālaṇa*[.]and not as the daughter's son of *Sātana*.—K. V. Ramesh].
- 4 The last part of the tithi *myām* now existing, suggests that it may be *ṛaṅchami* or like.
- 5 [See Note 17 below.—K. V. Ramesh].
- 6 *C.II.*, Vol. III, No. 19.

SHANKARPUR PLATE OF BUDHAGUPTA AND HARIVARMAN

- 7 [See Note 17 below.—K.V. Ramesh].
- 8 *Ep. Ind.*, Vol. XV, 134 and 138.
- 9 *Ibid.*, Vol. XIV, p. 115.
- 10 *CII.*, Vol. III, p. 219, No. 47.
- 11 The first letter of the name is doubtful and carelessly engraved. If we take this name to be a mistake for Bhimavarman, then reference may be invited to the Kōsam stone image inscription of *Mahārāja* Bhimavarman of year 139. See, *ASR*, Vol. I, pp. 309 ff.; Vol. X, p. 3 and *CII.*, Vol. III, No. 65.
- 12 A pillar inscription of the time of Skandagupta has been discovered from Supia near Rewa. See *Ep. Ind.*, XXXIII, p. 305.
- 13 The second letter of the name of this king is of a peculiar type. If the correct name is presumed to be Śāntana then the city of Śāntanapura mentioned in the Varanasi plates and identified with modern Satna may have been founded by him. *Proc. of 12th Ori. Con.*, p. 593 quoted by Parmanandgupta in *Geography in Ancient Indian Inscriptions*, p. 104. [This letter is more likely *la* and less likely *rya*.—K. V. Ramesh].
- 14 *CII.*, Vol. III, Nos. 26 and 31.
- 15 From original plate.
- 16 Expressed by a symbol.
- 17 [The correct reading of the date portion is *Samvatsara-sha(śa)l(ē)=shṭa-shashṭyuta(tta)rē* which will mean that the plate in question was actually issued in Gupta year 168 (= 487-88 A. D.) and not in 166 as stated by the learned author.—K.V. Ramesh].
- 18 The letter is broken.
- 19 Since the letters are carelessly engraved the reading is doubtful. [See foot note 3 above.—K. V. Ramesh].
20. [The intended reading is *Sri-Yashjarājena*.—K. V. Ramesh].

11. PALLAVA QUEEN RANGAPATAKA'S INSCRIPTION

Michael Lockwood

A. Vishnu Bhat

The Kailāsanātha temple at Kāñchīpuram is rich with inscriptions of its builder, the Pallava king Narasiṃhavarman II (Rājasimha), as well as his son, Mahēndravarmān III. In front of the main temple complex, just outside its enclosing wall, are several small shrines which belong to the same period. On three of these small shrines are some inscriptions which relate to their foundation by other members of the royal family.

E. Hultsch, who edited and translated the Kailāsanātha temple inscriptions in Volume I (1890) of *South Indian Inscriptions* (Nos. 28-30), included in that volume the inscriptions found on the small shrines in front. The most notable of these inscriptions was the Sanskrit poetry of three verses ascribed to queen Raṅgapatākā.

R. Nagaswamy has recently noticed an error in Hultsch's location of 'Raṅgapatākā's inscription. Hultsch located the verse which contains the name 'Raṅgapatākā' on the facade of the third shrine to the right of the front entrance to the main temple complex. But this is not its correct position. This verse is actually found on the facade of the FIFTH shrine to the right of the front entrance.

This error in location is serious because the verse which contains the name 'Raṅgapatākā' does not stand alone. Hultsch read it in conjunction with two other verses which actually are to be found on the third shrine. But now we shall have to read the 'Raṅgapatākā' verse in conjunction

with the two different verses found on FIFTH shrine!

Because of this mistaken juxtaposition of verses, Hultsch and all scholars since his day have unquestioningly thought Raṅgapatākā to be the queen of Narasiṃha II. For a clearer understanding of why they did so, we give below, in the order in which Hultsch presented them in the *SII.*, Vol. I the several verses inscribed on the third and fifth shrines.

Here is Hultsch's translation along with his location of the various verses:

On the third shrine to the right of the front entrance on the facade, first line (*SII.*, I, No. 29):

Adoration to Śiva!

(Verse 1) She, who was the dearly beloved mistress of her husband, the supreme lord, who was famed by the name of Kālakāla, whose sign was the bull, and the strength of whose bow had become manifest at the destruction of cities, just as the daughter of the king of mountains (*Pārvatī*) is, the dearly beloved mistress of her husband, the supreme lord (*Śiva*), whose sign is the bull, and the strength of whose bow has become manifest at the destruction of (*the demon*) Pura;

ON THE BACK

(Verse 2) She, who is resplendent, as she has attained the mighty position